

GINNNGER

From Barriers to Action

Policy Insights for Advancing Urban
Regeneration in Europe

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About GINNGER

The GINNGER project aims to create new, inclusive, and participatory processes for **neighbourhood regeneration**. A **methodology** to support **collaborative decision-making** is at the project's core. GINNGER is also designing and implementing regeneration plans at six pilot sites in Europe: Langreo (Spain), Plovdiv (Bulgaria), Massagno (Switzerland), Murcia (Spain), Orte (Italy), and Paris (France). Four key areas of regeneration are involved: energy efficiency, renovation of buildings and urban spaces, efficient use of resources, and sustainable mobility.

**GINNGER | Co-designing
neighbourhood regeneration**

Policy context

A fragmented framework

Sustainable and inclusive neighbourhood regeneration in the EU is shaped by strategic initiatives such as the **European Green Deal**¹, the **Renovation Wave**², and the **Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities**³. In parallel, soft-law instruments, including the **Urban Agenda for the EU**⁴ and the **New European Bauhaus**⁵ initiative, reinforce integrated, place-based approaches, citizen participation, and quality of the built environment.

However, translating these EU objectives into local practice faces **fragmented competencies** across governance levels, **limited integration** of participatory processes in planning, and **limited administrative capacity** at the municipal level.

Challenges and policy recommendations

Sustainable **neighbourhood regeneration** across Europe

Comparing the legislative frameworks of the GINUNGER's pilot cities⁶ reveals a **tension between ambition and implementation capacity in inclusive and sustainable neighbourhoods that is common to various European countries**. Although most of them have instruments that support urban regeneration and energy efficiency, they face persistent **regulatory fragmentation and administrative burdens** that slow the execution of integrated approaches. The analysis carried out by GINUNGER has identified a **set of common challenges and to related policy recommendations**.

Challenges and policy recommendations

Challenges		Recommendations
<p>Fragmented multi-level governance and unclear operational guidance, and subsequent misalignment between EU objectives, national regulations, and local planning.</p>	1	<p>Strengthen multi-level governance and coordination mechanisms by providing clearer operational guidance and encouraging better alignment between EU objectives, national regulations, and local planning practices.</p>
<p>Short funding horizons and weak requirements for participation and impact monitoring.</p>	2	<p>Support long-term, neighbourhood-scale regeneration by extending funding horizons and embedding requirements for participatory processes and impact monitoring, thereby improving the scalability and durability of regeneration outcomes across Member States.</p>
<p>EU buildings and energy policies largely focused on individual buildings, rather than on districts.</p>	3	<p>Embed neighbourhood-scale regeneration as an operational unit in EU building/energy policy implementation. Encourage Member States to recognise neighbourhood/district-level renovation plans as eligible compliance pathways and encourage alignment of renovation roadmaps.</p>

Challenges and policy recommendations

Challenges		Recommendations
<p>Insufficient citizen participation and co-creation in the practice of neighbourhood regeneration.</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>Make citizen co-creation and participation enforceable, introducing minimum requirements for participatory governance in EU-funded regeneration programmes and promote EU-level guidance to help Member States translate participation principles into planning procedures.</p>
<p>Regulatory uncertainty and fragmented rules for energy sharing and renewable energy communities, with subsequent limitation to their deployment, replication, and investment attractiveness.</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>Remove regulatory barriers for renewable energy communities and energy sharing at the neighbourhood scale. Clarify and standardise practical rules for energy sharing, collective self-consumption, grid access, and revenue sharing to reduce legal uncertainty; promote interoperable, replicable legal/contractual templates for the set-up of renewable energy communities.</p>
<p>Conflicting heritage protection and energy efficiency regulations.</p>	<p>6</p>	<p>Resolve the 'heritage protection vs. energy renovation' regulatory deadlock. Promote EU-level harmonised guidance that enables proportionate energy upgrades in protected buildings and historic districts (e.g., approved solution catalogues, simplified authorisations for low-impact measures).</p>

Challenges and policy recommendations

Challenges		Recommendations
<p>Lack of clear EU-level incentives and operational requirements for circular renovation, with subsequent limitation of circularity practices.</p>	7	<p>Create EU-level incentives and clearer rules for circular renovation and adaptive reuse. Strengthen EU guidance on circularity in renovation by requiring material passports, pre-demolition audits, reuse targets, and circular procurement criteria in publicly supported regeneration.</p>
<p>Fragmented permitting procedures and limited local administrative capacity.</p>	8	<p>Reduce administrative fragmentation through one-stop shops and simplified permitting. Encourage Member States to implement one-stop-shop models for neighbourhood regeneration (technical, legal, and funding assistance), especially for medium-sized municipalities with limited capacity; recommend streamlined approval procedures for regeneration projects to align environmental assessment, planning permissions, and energy-related authorisations.</p>
<p>Absence of shared standards for participatory processes, data governance and performance monitoring.</p>	9	<p>Enable standardisation and market uptake of GINGER-type solutions. Support the development of EU-level standards or guidelines for participatory regeneration processes, neighbourhood-level energy data governance, and performance monitoring of integrated regeneration plans.</p>

Conclusions and next steps

This policy brief presents preliminary EU-focused recommendations, **based on GINUNGER's pilots' experience**, aimed at supporting authorities and policymakers to **facilitate and standardise neighbourhood renovation** and **collaborative decision-making** at the European level.

During the next months, the project partners will expand this analysis, identifying **best practices and potential areas for harmonisation** in the four key areas of regeneration (energy efficiency, renovation of buildings and urban spaces, efficient use of resources, and sustainable mobility). Moreover, **tailored policy briefs for each country involved in GINUNGER will be released and distributed to local authorities.**

Methodology

The analysis presented was based on a desk review of national and EU legislation, complemented by data collected through the assessment of policy and regulatory drivers and barriers (conducted under GINUNGER's Task 2.4), and through questionnaires circulated among pilot partners.

Sources and further information

- ¹ [The European Green Deal - European Commission](#)
- ² [Renovation wave](#)
- ³ [Climate-neutral and smart cities - Research and innovation](#)
- ⁴ [Urban Agenda for the EU | EUI](#)
- ⁵ [New European Bauhaus: beautiful, sustainable, together](#)
- ⁶ See "Methodology" section

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